

The Effect of Work Load and Burnout on Nurses on the Implementation of Patient Safety in Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 09 July 2022	Background: Nurses are medical personnel who have a big role in the hospital, The job descriptions of nurses are very large and time consuming. The workload that is owned is sometimes very large, causing Burnout, it is feared that the burnout will affect the implementation of patient safety. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of burnout workload on nurses on the implementation of patient safety Methods: This research is a type of quantitative research that is observational with a cross-sectional design. Samples were taken from 6 wards, 54 nurses. Data analysis using kruskal-wallis. Results: The analysis showed that there was an influence between workload and implementation of <i>patient safety</i> ($p = 0.029$; $p < 0.05$). The analysis showed that there was an influence between <i>burnout</i> and the implementation of <i>patient safety</i> ($p = 0.033$; $p < 0.05$) Conclusion: there is a influence between burnout and workload on the implementation of patient safety on nurses at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul.
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KEYWORDS: Workload; Burnout; Nurses; Patient safety implementation	

I. PRELIMINARY

Nurses are medical personnel who have a big role in the hospital, the jobdesk of nurses is very much and takes time.[1] In 2011, the first quarter of the Hospital Patient Safety Committee reported, patient safety incident reports were 11, 23% occurred in the nursing unit, 6.17% in the pharmacy unit, and 4.12% by doctors.[2] This is because the treatment room in the hospital is the place that contributes the most to patient care. As a place that is directly in touch with patients, there is a very large risk of errors or patient safety incidents. [3] High demands from society can unconsciously create a mental workload for nurses when carrying out their duties. Although often this mental workload is not visible from the outside, it greatly affects the performance of nurses in carrying out their duties, so that this can directly affect the level of work. patient satisfaction. [4] Burnout is a term that describes the emotional condition of a person who feels tired and bored mentally, emotionally and physically as a result of increased work demands. [5] Burnout is a work-related syndrome that most often affects.[6] It should be a big concern for the hospital as a service provider. This aspect is related to the implementation of patient safety.

II. METHOD

This research is a type of quantitative research that is observational with a cross-sectional design. In this study, observations were made to nurses at Panembahan Senopati Hospital. This study involved 6 wards with a total population of 120 nurses and a sample of 54 nurses was taken. The inclusion criteria were nurses at Panembahan Senopati Bantul Hospital who were willing to fill out the questionnaire. Nurses at Panembahan Senopati Bantul Hospital who work in inpatient wards and work at least 1 year. The tools used in this study were the Workload Measurement questionnaire. The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) questionnaire was used to measure nurses' burnout. The data for patient safety implementation was taken from a questionnaire that was adjusted to the 6 patient safety goals at the hospital. The study was conducted from October 2020 to December 2020.

The research begins with an explanation of the aims and objectives of the study, then if the nurse is willing to become a research respondent, they will be asked to fill out the workload questionnaire, the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) and the Patient safety implementation questionnaire

III. RESULT

Overview of Panembahan Senopati Hospital

Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul is one of the public hospitals in the Special Region of Yogyakarta, precisely in the district of Bantul, Indonesia. Panembahan Senopati Hospital is accredited B as a regional hospital

Overview of Laboratory Units

The laboratory unit of the Selogiri Muhamamdiyah Hospital provides a variety of laboratory services. Six analysts provide laboratory services. The profile of the tool is as follows:

Table 1. Nurse characteristic

Variabel	Frequency	Presentage
Age		
21-30 Years old	14	25,9
31-40 Years old	24	44,4
41-50 Years old	12	22,2
> 50 tahun	4	7,4
Gender		
Male	8	14,8
Female	46	85,2
Marriage		
Married	42	77,8
Single	12	22,2
Degree		
D3	30	55,6
S1	24	44,4
Leght of Working		
1-5 years	19	35,2
5-10 years	18	33,3
> 10 years	17	31,5

Table 1 shows that the majority of the subjects of this study were 31-40 years old (44.4%), female (85.2%), married (77.8%), D3 education (55.6%), and had worked for 1-5 years (35.2%).

Table 2. Overview of Workload, Burnout Rate, and Implementation of Patient safety

Variabel	Frequency	Presentage
Beban Kerja		
Light	19	35,2
Moderate	20	37,0
Heavy	15	27,8
Burnout		
Low	17	31,5
Moderate	17	31,5
High	20	37,0
Implementasi Patient safety		
Good	26	48,1
Average	19	35,2
Bad	9	16,7
Total	54	100,0

Table 2 shows that the majority of the subjects of this study felt a workload that was included in the moderate category (37%), felt burnout in the high category level (37%), and implemented patient safety well (48.1%).

Table 3. The Influence Between Workload and Burnout with the Implementation of Patient safety

		Implementasi <i>Patient safety</i>			Nilai <i>p</i>	
		Good	Average	Bad		
Workload	Light	N	11	3	0,029	
		%	20,4%	5,6%		9,3%
	Moderate	N	10	7		3
		%	18,5%	13,0%		5,6%
	Heavy	N	5	9		1
		%	9,3%	16,7%		1,9%
Burnout	Low	N	8	7	0,033	
		%	14,8%	13,0%		3,7%
	Moderate	N	7	7		3
		%	13,0%	13,0%		5,6%
	High	N	11	5		4
		%	20,4%	9,3%		7,4%
Total	N	26	19	9		
	%	48.1%	35,2%	16,7%		

Table 3 shows that for nurses who feel they have a light and moderate workload, the majority implement patient safety which is in the good category, while for nurses who feel they have a heavy workload, the majority implement patient safety which is included in the moderate category. The analysis showed that there was an influence between workload and implementation of patient safety ($p = 0.029$; $p < 0.05$).

It can also be seen that the nurses who felt burnout were in the low and high categories, the majority carried out the implementation of patient safety which was in the good category, while the nurses who felt that they had burnout were in the moderate category, the majority carried out the implementation of patient safety which was included in the good and moderate categories with the number the same many. The analysis showed that there was an influence between burnout and the implementation of patient safety ($p = 0.033$; $p < 0.05$).

The results of this study indicate that the majority of the subjects of this study were 31-40 years old (44.4%), female (85.2%), married (77.8%), D3 education (55.6%), and have worked for 1-5 years (35.2%). The cross tabulation results show that for nurses who feel they have a light and moderate workload, the majority implement patient safety which is in the good category, while for nurses who feel they have a heavy workload, the majority implement patient safety which is included in the moderate category. The analysis showed that there was an influence between workload and implementation of patient safety ($p = 0.029$; $p < 0.05$).

These results are in line with a study conducted by Kusumaningrum (2020) at the Simo Boyolali Regional General Hospital, Central Java. This study with a cross sectional design involving 59 nurses aims to determine the effect of nursing workload on nurses' performance in implementing patient safety. The study found that most had a heavy workload (63%) and had a good performance in implementing patient safety (51%). The results of the analysis show that there is a significant

influence between workload and nurse performance in the implementation of patient safety at Simo Boyolali Hospital. This influence is found to have a strength that is weak with and the direction is opposite. This means that the greater the workload, the worse the nurse's performance in implementing patient safety [7]

Similar results were also obtained in a study conducted by Rita (2020) at Muhammadiyah Hospital, Lamongan, East Java. This study with a cross sectional design involving 28 nurses aims to determine the effect of nurses' workload on compliance with patient safety implementation. The study found that most of the nurses had a moderate workload (60.7%) and had adequate patient safety implementation compliance (64.3%). The results of the analysis show that there is an influence between the workload of nurses and compliance with the implementation of patient safety.[8]

Another study that also found results that support this research is a study conducted by Ratnaningsih (2020) at Panembahan Senopati Bantul Hospital, DI Yogyakarta. This study with a cross sectional design involving 33 nurses aims to determine the effect of nurses' workload on the implementation of patient safety. The study found that the workload of nurses in inpatient rooms was high (57.6%) and most implementation of patient safety was sufficient (39.4%). The results of the analysis show that there is an influence between the workload of nurses and the implementation of patient safety [9]

This study also found that nurses who felt burnout were in the low and high categories, the majority carried out patient safety which was in the good category, while for nurses who felt that they had burnout in the moderate category, the majority carried out the implementation of patient safety which was in the good and moderate categories with the same amount. The analysis showed that there was an influence between burnout and the implementation of patient safety ($p = 0.033$; $p < 0.05$).

These results are in line with a study conducted by Suki (2018) at Dr. Soepraoen Hospital Malang, East Java. The study with a cross sectional design involving 99 nurses aimed to analyze the effect of burnout syndrome nurses and patient safety climate in the inpatient installation. The instruments used in this study were the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) questionnaire and the Safety Attitudes Questionnaire (SAQ). The study found that there was a negative influence between nurses' burnout syndrome and the patient safety climate [10]

Another study that also shows relatively identical results to this study is a study conducted by Hall (2016). This research with a systematic review design aims to explain the occurrence of burnout in nurses and what effect it has on patient safety. The study found that burnout in nurses occurred when there were problems with task components, working conditions, individual characteristics, and energy. The existence of a problem in one of these components has an effect on decreasing performance in providing health services, including increasing the risk of problems with patient safety [11]. Similar results were also shown in a study conducted by Liu (2019) in 23 hospitals in Guangdong, China. The study with a cross sectional design involving 1,502 nurses aimed to determine the effect of burnout on nurses on patient safety. One of the results of this study found that burnout in nurses has an effect on patient safety [12]

Research conducted by Garcia (2019) also shows results that support this study. Research with a systematic review design with a meta-analysis involving 21 studies aims to determine the effect of burnout on nurses on patient safety. The study found that the majority of the studies analyzed indicated an influence between burnout and poor implementation of patient safety. High levels of fatigue are more common in doctors and nurses. This condition is related to external factors, such as high workloads, long trips, and ineffective interpersonal influences [13]

IV. CONCLUSION AND LIMITATION

Conclusion

From the research that has been conducted on nurses who work at Panembahan Senopati Bantul Hospital, it can be concluded that the workload of nurses at Panembahan Senopati Bantul Hospital has an effect on the implementation of patient safety. Burnout that occurs in nurses at Panembahan Senopati Bantul Hospital has an effect on the implementation of patient safety.

Limitation

This research has several limitations in its implementation, including:

1. This study uses a cross sectional so that it cannot find the cause and effect between variables.
2. Unexamined confounding variables may be factors that influence the results of the study.

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